

COST Action CA22146

**Harnessing the potential of underutilized crops to promote
sustainable food production (DIVERSICROP)**

Mission report

**Modern Online Foraging Communities: Shaping New Trends in
Wild Food Use**

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This report provides the background and results of the mission *Modern Online Foraging Communities: Shaping New Trends in Wild Food Use*. It has been prepared with publication on the Diversicrop website and related platforms in mind.

Summary

This STSM investigated the Slovenian foraging communities, particularly focusing on how social media facilitates knowledge transfer among foragers. The study involved 31 semi-structured interviews with Slovenian foragers, ranging from enthusiastic amateurs to semi-professional and professional foragers. The interviews explored participants' backgrounds, motivations, use of social media, and the plant species they commonly feature in their educational activities.

One of the key findings is the significant role social media plays in the dissemination of foraging knowledge. Nearly all participants use platforms like Facebook and Instagram to reach their audiences, with many combining educational content on plant identification and safety with promotional activities. Social media is not only a tool for self-promotion but also a critical avenue for educating others about sustainable foraging practices. However, despite the effectiveness of these platforms, most foragers remain reluctant to adopt newer platforms like TikTok, citing reasons such as time constraints and a perception that their target audiences are older and less likely to use these platforms.

The study also found a growing sense of community among Slovenian foragers, fostered by events like the Festival nabiralništva and FesDivjal. These festivals have helped solidify connections within the community, offering workshops, talks, and other activities that bring together like-minded individuals.

This research emphasizes the potential of wild food plants (WFPs) in contributing to sustainable food systems. As traditional knowledge bearers fade, foraging instructors are becoming key figures in preserving and disseminating knowledge about WFPs, which could play a crucial role in diversifying food sources and promoting environmental sustainability. Future collaborations aim to further explore the role of wild plants in food security and their place in contemporary and traditional foraging practices.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a significant rise in online foraging communities. These groups gather on platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube, sharing information and experiences. Moderators of these communities often achieve renowned status by collaborating with well-known chefs, appearing on TV shows, and participating in culinary events. As a result, they frequently become trendsetters in foraging and wild food use.

The emergence of the internet and social media has significantly impacted various disciplines, including food science, agronomy, and nature conservation (Šmelhausová et al., 2022). A recent essay by De Meyer & Ceuterick (2022) highlighted that social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and YouTube, as well as internet forums, serve as valuable sources of information on natural resources, agricultural practices, and innovations. These platforms contain a wealth of ethnobotanical information, indicating their high ethnobiological value. This recognition has led to the development of protocols for extracting data from social media (e.g., Chowdhury et al., 2023).

In recent years, particularly due to the Coronavirus pandemic, there has been a notable rise in online foraging communities. Behind each social media channel, there are moderators with varying motivations, ranging from enthusiastic amateur foragers to professional foragers employing strategic marketing. These moderators often work with renowned chefs and advise on healthy eating habits, sometimes achieving influencer status (Dekoninck et al., 2023).

While these foragers benefit from their online presence, they also bear the responsibility of providing accurate information about plant use, cautioning against dangerous plants, addressing ethical and legal issues in foraging, and promoting fair and sustainable practices.

Description of the work

The aim of this research was to explore the digital landscape of social media in plant foraging communities from both the moderators' and users' perspectives. Using Slovenian foraging communities as a case study, this research involved:

- a. Scanning different social media platforms for Slovenian foraging communities.
- b. Understanding the motivations of foraging instructors through interviews with a range of foragers, from amateurs to (semi)professionals.
- c. Establishing a list of plant species promoted by (semi)professional foragers.

We prepared an interview with the aim to understand the ways how knowledge is obtained and transferred to the participants of the educational events and to the followers on social media. The interview included the following topics and questions:

Background Information

- Age, formal education, current work, and location of current work.

Event Types

- What kinds of events do you organize regarding wild plants?

Income from Foraging

- If foraging contributes to your income, what is the financial ratio between your various activities?

Importance of Social Media

- How important is social media for you as a forager? Which platforms do you use the most, and why?

Learning via Social Media

- Have you ever used social media to learn or obtain new information about plants?

Time Spent on Social Media

- How many hours per week do you dedicate to managing your social media?

Follower Interaction

- Do you interact with your followers? If yes, how often and why?

Social Media Content

- What are the main topics or types of content you share on your social media?

Income from Social Media

- Do you earn any income indirectly through social media?

Impact of Social Media on Success

- Do you think you are more successful or visible because you use social media?

Preferred Platforms for Foraging Education

- In your opinion, which social media platforms are best for interacting with or educating others about foraging?

Evaluating Media Usage

- Do you feel that some of the platforms you use are outdated, and are you considering switching to new ones?

Experience as a Foraging Instructor

- How many years have you worked as a foraging instructor?

Modes of Educational Activities

- Are the activities you organize conducted in person, online, or both? Is there an age difference between participants in these two modes?

Online vs. Live Courses

- If you offer online courses, what are the benefits and disadvantages for participants compared to live courses?

Commonly Foraged Items

- What are the most commonly foraged items used in your courses (approximately 10)?

Identification as a Forager

- Do you consider yourself a forager?

Path to Foraging

- When did you start considering yourself a forager? What led you to this path?

Impact of Formal Education

- Has your formal education significantly influenced how you forage?

Sense of Community

- Do you feel that, as a forager, you belong to a community (either official or unofficial)?

Influential Books, Films, or Websites

- Were there any books, films, or websites that influenced you?

Important Figures in Foraging

- Can you name around five people who have been significant to you as a forager? For each, please state their relationship to you.

Significant Plants

- Please list up to five plants that are important to you. Can you explain why these plants are significant? Are they connected to your memories, the environment where you grew up, or where you live now?

Conservation Concerns

- How important are conservation issues to you when it comes to foraging?

Species Overexploitation

- Do you think there are any species that are being overexploited by foragers? If yes, which ones?

After the preparation of the interview questions, we searched for adequate respondents. We selected the respondents first based on the participation in the 1st and 2nd foraging festivals held in 2023 and 2024, and then used the snowball effect to obtain more participants. The participants were contacted mostly through the social media (Facebook or Instagram) or by email. We were able to perform 31 semi-structured on-line interviews. The interviews were performed on the platform ZOOM and lasted from 30 to 60 minutes. Interviews were recorded and transcribed with the use of the automatic service provided by Office 365. After the interviews, responses were transferred into a table for further analysis.

Figure 1: Example of an on-line interview with the participant Lovro Vehovar from the herbal farm Korina, conducted on July 1, 2024 from the premises of University of Pollenzo.

Results, outcome and longer-term implications

About the study

The study involved 31 participants, comprising 22 females and 9 males. Participants ranged in age from 26 to 61 years, with an average age of 42.5 years. A significant majority, 87%, hold a university degree or higher (Master's or PhD), while 13% have a high school diploma. Among those with a university degree, 55.6% have a background in natural sciences, and 18.5% have degrees in ethnology, geography, sociology, or anthropology.

The geographic distribution of respondents was uneven. The majority (26%) were from the Osrednjeslovenska region, followed by 16% from both the Goriška and Gorenjska regions, and 13% from the Podravska region.

Use of Social Media

Nearly all participants use social media and emphasize its importance in reaching their target audience. Facebook and Instagram are the most widely used platforms, with 93.5% and 64.5% of participants utilizing them, respectively. Some foragers also use other channels such as websites, YouTube, LinkedIn, mailing lists, and LinkTree. Although a few considered adopting newer platforms like TikTok, most are unlikely to do so. The reasons cited include lack of time, lack of interest, and a belief that their followers or target audience are not part of the younger generation that primarily uses these newer platforms, but rather the older generation accustomed to Facebook.

Social media is used both for self-promotion and for educational purposes, such as presenting information on useful and poisonous species, and alternative uses of various species. Most foraging educators combine both approaches in their online presence.

Identification with the Term "Forager" and the Foraging Community

Out of 30 respondents, 19 identify with the term "nabiralec" (forager), although the definition is somewhat ambiguous, leading to highly personal interpretations. Some participants do not consider themselves foragers because they do not collect enough to warrant the label, while others identify as foragers even though they collect only occasionally. Additionally, some participants, including those actively involved in sharing their knowledge about wild plants, prefer to call themselves (foraging) educators rather than foragers. Others identify more with the term herbalist, as their

activities focus primarily on medicinal herbs, which can be cultivated in gardens rather than exclusively collected in the wild.

Interviews reveal that the foraging community in Slovenia is growing, with a stronger sense of community emerging in recent years, particularly following the establishment of certain festivals. Among these, the Festival nabiralništva (Foraging Festival) and FesDivjal (WildFest) were frequently mentioned as pivotal in fostering a foraging community. The Festival nabiralništva, a two-day event that began in 2023, features workshops on wild plant foraging held simultaneously in various locations across Slovenia on the first day. On the second day, foragers gather at the Ljubljana market to showcase their activities, with several online talks preceding the live event. The other event, FesDivjal, was first organized in 2022 in the Kozjansko Regional Park. This three-day event offers workshops, talks, and nature walks, with participants able to camp in designated areas within the park. These events, attended by like-minded individuals, have quickly contributed to a strong sense of belonging within the foraging community.

Organization of Educational Activities

The educational activities organized by foragers are diverse, ranging from live and online lectures to nature walks and foraging workshops that combine foraging with cooking. Workshops also cover topics such as product preparation (e.g., soaps, creams, scents), distillation techniques, and specialized food preparation methods like fermenting wild foods and creating cocktails from wild ingredients. In addition to these educational offerings, some foragers provide non-educational activities, such as combining foraging workshops with yoga classes, women's circles, storytelling events, making midsummer flower wreaths, thematic baby showers or bachelorette parties, and healing walks in the woods.

Some participants have specialized in advanced courses, particularly in the field of medicinal plants, and offer specialized training for professionals, including medical doctors, pharmacists, and veterinarians. Several of these courses have received accreditation, allowing professionals to use them as part of their continuing education requirements.

Figure 2: A collage of photos taken at a foraging workshop at University of Pollenzo (July 8, 2024).

Plants Presented in Educational Activities

Respondents were asked to provide a list of approximately 10 plant species they commonly present in their educational activities. Two respondents provided lists of mushrooms (not included here), and two others were not involved in any educational activities, so they did not provide any species. In total, the compiled list includes 116 plant taxa. Over half of the respondents mentioned *Urtica dioica*, *Plantago* species (including *P. major* and *P. lanceolata*), and *Achillea millefolium*, followed by *Taraxacum officinale*, *Allium ursinum*, *Sambucus nigra*, and *Aposeris foetida*. Figure 1 presents the plants mentioned by over 10% of the respondents.

Figure 2: Plant taxa most frequently mentioned by foraging instructors.

Motivations and Knowledge Sources of Slovenian Forager Instructors

Grivins (2021) categorized foragers into four groups based on their motivations and knowledge frameworks: rooted foragers, lifestyle foragers, subsistence foragers, and commercial foragers. To establish a similar classification for Slovenian forager instructors, we asked participants about their sources of knowledge and inspiration. Their responses resulted in a list of 48 books (or book series), movies, TV shows, and various online resources (Figure 3). Most of the books cited are non-fiction, covering topics such as edible wild plants, medicinal plants, sustainable agriculture, permaculture, and cooking. Slovenian and foreign non-fiction books are represented in roughly equal measure. Additionally, several respondents mentioned children's books and TV shows as early influences that shaped their interest in foraging.

Figure 3. Sources of inspiration mentioned by foraging instructors.

Among the influential figures, both living and deceased, Slovenian and foreign, fictional and non-fictional, one name was mentioned by over 50% of the respondents: Dario Cortese (Figure 4). A Slovenian agronomist, Cortese became a prominent advocate for foraging in Slovenia. He authored several books on wild plant use well before the foraging trend gained popularity across Europe. Referred to by many respondents as the "father of foragers," Cortese passed away at a relatively young age in 2021. Several respondents attended his courses and workshops, learning directly from him. Other notable Slovenian figures mentioned as sources of inspiration and information include Katja Rebolj, Luka Kristanc, Tina Mele, Karmen Gajšek, Andreja Papež Kristanc, and Uroš Švigelj, all of whom were also interviewed for this study.

In contrast, foreign foragers or other personalities were mentioned only sporadically, with no single name standing out.

Figure 4. Network representing foraging instructors (numbers 1-30) and persons they mention as being important for their activities related to wild plant uses.

Longer-term implications and relation to Diversicrop

Not being regarded as crops, the topic of wild food plants is not directly connected to Diversicrop main aims. However, wild food plants (WFPs) have been an important source of human nutrition since ancient times. In the times of abundance, people turn to more nutritious food sources, such as agricultural crops, and WFPs represent only a welcome addition to the people's diet. However, in times when conventional food is not available due to emergency situations, such as natural disasters and conflicts, wild food plants can represent an important way of survival (Redžič 2010, Sulaiman et al. 2022).

Despite the recent increase of interest in WFPs, they are at present still underutilised, and known to a restricted number of people, especially those who spend more time in nature and are open to new ideas. However, WFPs could contribute to the diversification of food sources and rethinking our food systems, as well as lower our impact on nature, as several WFPs are weeds and ruderal species that colonize disturbed sites and their collection has no negative impact on nature.

Since the goal of Diversicrop is to contribute to a more diverse, environmentally sustainable farming and food systems and by rethinking our food systems, it is essential to preserve knowledge about WFPs and adapt it to new circumstances. With the disappearance of the knowledgeable village elders, foraging instructors could replace this gap. It is therefore important to understand if and how knowledge about these plants is transferred to the society.

Personal Development, Networking, and Capacity Building

The Short-Term Scientific Mission (STSM) provided me with the opportunity to join a small team of ethnobotanists at the University of Pollenzo, a renowned institution specializing in food studies,

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including the study of wild food plants. The university employs two distinguished ethnobotanists: Professor Andrea Pieroni and Assistant Professor Naji Sulaiman.

Figure 5: Chiara Romano, Andrea Pieroni, Živa Fišer and Naji Sulaiman in front of University of Pollenzo (June 27, 2024).

During my stay, I gained insight into the operations of a private university, attended several student final presentations, and visited the university's garden, which is managed by the students, as well as some other local herbal gardens. The university garden not only serves as an educational resource but also produces vegetables used in the preparation of meals at the university cafeteria. Additionally, I had the privilege of participating in a foraging workshop led by Naji Sulaiman. This workshop extended into the Pollenzo Food Lab, where experienced chefs demonstrated innovative ways to prepare wild food plants.

Figure 6: Plants in one of the local herbal gardens in Scaparoni.

The workshop was particularly relevant to my research, which focuses on how foraging instructors conduct workshops and present wild food plants. This experience enriched my understanding and will contribute to the advancement of my work.

Figure 7: A collage of photos from the university and its garden (June 6, 2024).

I also had the opportunity to join Professor Andrea Pieroni and Professor Abdelkader Ammam, a visiting professor from Algeria, on a visit to a local community in the Alps. During this visit, we explored a mountain farm that continues to practice traditional dairy production while also seeking innovative approaches to food production, such as incorporating wild plants collected from the region.

Figure 8: A collage of photos from the visit of the mountain farm in the Alps near Pramollo (June 21, 2024).

These new connections will allow me to deepen my focus on wild food plants and open up opportunities for further collaboration. For instance, Naji Sulaiman is scheduled to give a talk titled

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"Ethnobiology of Wartime: Where Wild Plants are Crucial for Food Security" as part of the *Biological Evenings 2024/25* lecture series, organized by the Department of Biodiversity at the University of Primorska. His talk will be held online on February 12, 2025, at 7:00 PM.

Additionally, the current research is planned for submission to the special issue "*Wild Food Plants-Euphoria: Navigating the Relations between Contemporary and 'Traditional' Foraging*" of the journal *Economic Botany*.

Selected literature:

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